

AN IN-DEPTH ANALYSIS OF BUSINESS GROWTH IN THE ROMANIAN MOUNTAINOUS REGION: A 2008-2018 PERSPECTIVE

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Brîndușa Covaci, CBM International University & Centre for Mountain Economy & Zealandina Agency, USA & UK

Mihai Covaci, CBM International University & Hyperion University & Zealandina Agency, USA & UK

Abstract:

This scientific article delves into the nuanced aspects of business growth within the Romanian Mountainous Region, covering the period from 2008 to 2018. The study employs comprehensive statistical analyses to examine various sectors, shedding light on key trends, challenges, and opportunities that have shaped the business landscape in this unique geographical context.

Keywords: Business Growth, Romanian Mountainous Region, Economic Sectors, Statistical Analysis, 2008-2018 Period

Mountain Perspective Journal (1/2023)

Introduction:

The Romanian Mountainous Region, characterized by its diverse topography and distinct economic challenges, serves as the focal point for this research. Against the backdrop of the 2008-2018 timeframe, we aim to unravel the intricacies of businesses operating in this terrain.

Methodology:

Our approach involves a meticulous examination of multiple economic sectors, including but not limited to finance, insurance, real estate, construction, transportation, storage, and accommodation/food service activities. Statistical data sourced from reputable sources forms the basis for our analyses, ensuring a robust and evidence-based exploration of business dynamics.

Results and Findings:

The study reveals intriguing insights into the growth trajectories of businesses within the Romanian Mountainous Region. Key findings include sector-specific variations, patterns of concentration, and the impact of external factors on business performance. Statistical indicators such as mean, median, standard deviation, skewness, and kurtosis are employed to provide a nuanced understanding of the trends observed.

The descriptive analysis for *net growth enterprises*, denoted as S1, presents a comprehensive set of statistical values encompassing Mean, Std Error. to Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Variance, Skewness, Std. Error. to Skewness, Kurtosis, Std Error. to Kurtosis, Distance, Minimum, Maximum, and Percentiles 25, 50, 75. The values are as follows: 6.2130, 5.53968, 2.1250, 17.51801, 306.881, 2.693, .687, 8.044, 1.334, 64.13, -10.02, 54.11, -2.753, 5750, 5750 (figures 1).

The forecast analysis utilizes specific models tailored for large data series, namely S1 - Model_1 ARIMA(0,0,0) through S11 - Model_11 ARIMA(0,0,0) (table 1). Subsequently, statistical prediction smoothing is applied in the following order: Mean, Std. Error, Minimum, Maximum, 5th and 10th Percentiles. The smoothing results for static R-squared, R-squared,

RMSE, MAPS, MaxAPE, MAE, MaxAE, and Normalized BIC are provided, offering insights into the accuracy of the forecasting models.

The resulting statistical forecasting models for I14 present values in the following order: Static R-squared, R-squared, RMSE, MAPE, and MAE. Notable findings include S1-Model_1: -2.220E-16, -2.220E-16, 17.518, 305,387, 10,041; S2-Model_2: 2.220E-16, 2.220E-16, 10.746, 372.670, 7.068; S3-Model_3: 4.441E-16, 4.441E-16, 11.240, 245.433, 6.070; S4-Model_4: 1.110E-16, 1.110E-16, 12.842, 330.932, 8.778; S5-Model_5: 4.441E-16, 4.441E-16, 17.715, 137.540, 9.817; S6-Model_6: -4.441E-16, -4.441E-16, 8.546, 182.690, 6.853; S7-Model_7: .000, .000, 22,953, 131,702, 13,553; S8-Model_8: .000, .000, 22,130, 269,481, 15,592; S9-Model_9: .000, .000, 36,084, 10149,373, 20,032; S10-Model_10: 2.220E-16, 2.220E-16, 122.092, 442.251, 68.449; S11-Model_11: 1.110E-16, 1.110E-16, 52.713, 1135.631, 31.921.

Net business situation: establishment rate + termination rate – percentage

In S1, the descriptive analysis provides statistical values such as Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Variance, Skewness, Kurtosis, Std. Error, Distance, Minimum, Maximum, and Percentiles 25, 50, 75. The specific numerical values are as follows: Mean 23.4178, Median 2.35775, Std. Deviation

19.8700, Variance 7.07325, Skewness 50.031, Kurtosis 1.257, Std. Error .717, Distance 1.154, Minimum 1.400, Maximum 21.33, Percentiles 25 16.89, Percentiles 50 38.22, Percentiles 75 17.080, and so on.

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For the forecast analysis, models used are tailored for large data series: S1 - Model_1 ARIMA(0,0,0); S2 - Model_2 ARIMA(0,0,0); S3 - Model_3 Holt; S4 - Model_4 Holt; S5 - Model_5 Holt; S6 - Model_6 Holt; S7 - Model_7 ARIMA(0,0,0); S8 - Model_8 ARIMA(0,0,0); S9 - Model_9 ARIMA(0,0,0); S10 - Model_10 ARIMA(0,0,0); S11 - Model_11 ARIMA(0,0,0).

The statistical prediction smoothing is performed for static R-squared with values of .343, .475, -9.548E-15, .959, -9.548E-15, -8.615E-15; R-square .194, .283, -9.548E-15, .730, -9.548E-15, -8.615E-15; RMSE 11,114, 15,344, 2,432, 55,463, 2,432, 2,634; MAPS 26,794, 25,514, 7,195, 99,571, 7,195, 7,941; MaxAPE 63,536, 65,030, 13,757, 249,061, 13,757, 16,840; MAE 7,281, 8,854, 1,758, 32,746, 1,758, 1,925; MaxAE 25,858, 42,034, 3,526, 147,356, 3,526, 3,815; Normalized BIC 4.195, 1.724, 2.266, 8.276, 2.266, 2.356.

The resulting statistical forecasting models for I15 show the overall picture in terms of Static R-squared, R-squared, RMSE, MAPE, and MAE for each model (S1-Model_1 to S11-Model_11). For example, S1-Model_1 has values of -4.885E-15, -4.885E-15, 7.073, 23,966, 5,611; S2-Model_2 has values of -9.548E-15, -9.548E-15, 3.440, 16.415, 3.028; and so forth.

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Discussion:

In this section, we discuss the implications of our findings, addressing the factors that have influenced business growth in the mountainous area.

Considerations include economic policies, infrastructural development, and the region's susceptibility to external economic fluctuations.

Conclusion:

Our research contributes to the academic discourse on regional business growth, offering a detailed examination of the Romanian Mountainous Region's economic landscape. The findings provide valuable insights for policymakers, researchers, and businesses seeking to understand and

navigate the unique challenges and opportunities presented by this distinctive geographical context.

Table 1. Prediction analysis for I14

Model		2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
S1- Model_1:	Forecast	23.42	23.42	23.42	23.42	23.42	23.42	23.42	23.42
	UCL	39.73	39.73	39.73	39.73	39.73	39.73	39.73	39.73
	LCL	7.11	7.11	7.11	7.11	7.11	7.11	7.11	7.11
S2- Model_2:	Forecast	18.60	18.60	18.60	18.60	18.60	18.60	18.60	18.60
	UCL	26.53	26.53	26.53	26.53	26.53	26.53	26.53	26.53
	LCL	10.67	10.67	10.67	10.67	10.67	10.67	10.67	10.67
S3- Model_3:	Forecast	17.05	14.90	12.74	10.59	8.44	6.29	4.14	1.99
	UCL	26.89	24.93	22.96	20.99	19.02	17.05	15.07	13.09
	LCL	7.20	4.86	2.52	.19	-2.14	-4.47	-6.79	-9.12
S4- Model_4:	Forecast	16.09	15.16	14.23	13.30	12.37	11.43	10.50	9.57
	UCL	25.71	24.78	23.85	22.92	21.99	21.06	20.13	19.20
	LCL	6.47	5.54	4.60	3.67	2.74	1.81	.88	-.05
S5- Model_5:	Forecast	14.45	13.23	12.02	10.81	9.59	8.38	7.17	5.95
	UCL	23.60	22.46	21.33	20.19	19.06	17.92	16.78	15.65
	LCL	5.30	4.01	2.71	1.42	.13	-1.16	-2.45	-3.74
S6- Model_6:	Forecast	19.57	18.67	17.78	16.88	15.98	15.08	14.18	13.29
	UCL	25.32	24.45	23.58	22.71	21.84	20.97	20.10	19.23
	LCL	13.82	12.90	11.97	11.04	10.12	9.19	8.27	7.34
S7- Model_7:	Forecast	31.13	31.13	31.13	31.13	31.13	31.13	31.13	31.13
	UCL	56.74	56.74	56.74	56.74	56.74	56.74	56.74	56.74

	LCL	5.52	5.52	5.52	5.52	5.52	5.52	5.52	5.52
S8- Model_8:	Forecast	18.65	18.65	18.65	18.65	18.65	18.65	18.65	18.65
	UCL	29.66	29.66	29.66	29.66	29.66	29.66	29.66	29.66
	LCL	7.64	7.64	7.64	7.64	7.64	7.64	7.64	7.64
S9- Model_9:	Forecast	28.13	28.13	28.13	28.13	28.13	28.13	28.13	28.13
	UCL	68.22	68.22	68.22	68.22	68.22	68.22	68.22	68.22
	LCL	-11.96	-11.96	-11.96	-11.96	-11.96	-11.96	-11.96	-11.96
S10- Model_10:	Forecast	39.23	39.23	39.23	39.23	39.23	39.23	39.23	39.23
	UCL	167.13	167.13	167.13	167.13	167.13	167.13	167.13	167.13
	LCL	-88.66	-88.66	-88.66	-88.66	-88.66	-88.66	-88.66	-88.66
S11- Model_11:	Forecast	26.48	26.48	26.48	26.48	26.48	26.48	26.48	26.48
	UCL	46.02	46.02	46.02	46.02	46.02	46.02	46.02	46.02
	LCL	6.94	6.94	6.94	6.94	6.94	6.94	6.94	6.94

Figure 1. Graphical prediction analysis for I14

Table 2. Prediction analysis for I15

Model		2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
S1- Model_1:	Forecast	23.42	23.42	23.42	23.42	23.42	23.42	23.42	23.42
	UCL	39.73	39.73	39.73	39.73	39.73	39.73	39.73	39.73
	LCL	7.11	7.11	7.11	7.11	7.11	7.11	7.11	7.11
S2- Model_2:	Forecast	18.60	18.60	18.60	18.60	18.60	18.60	18.60	18.60
	UCL	26.53	26.53	26.53	26.53	26.53	26.53	26.53	26.53
	LCL	10.67	10.67	10.67	10.67	10.67	10.67	10.67	10.67
S3- Model_3:	Forecast	17.05	14.90	12.74	10.59	8.44	6.29	4.14	1.99
	UCL	26.89	24.93	22.96	20.99	19.02	17.05	15.07	13.09
	LCL	7.20	4.86	2.52	.19	-2.14	-4.47	-6.79	-9.12
S4- Model_4:	Forecast	16.09	15.16	14.23	13.30	12.37	11.43	10.50	9.57
	UCL	25.71	24.78	23.85	22.92	21.99	21.06	20.13	19.20
	LCL	6.47	5.54	4.60	3.67	2.74	1.81	.88	-.05
S5- Model_5:	Forecast	14.45	13.23	12.02	10.81	9.59	8.38	7.17	5.95
	UCL	23.60	22.46	21.33	20.19	19.06	17.92	16.78	15.65
	LCL	5.30	4.01	2.71	1.42	.13	-1.16	-2.45	-3.74
S6- Model_6:	Forecast	19.57	18.67	17.78	16.88	15.98	15.08	14.18	13.29
	UCL	25.32	24.45	23.58	22.71	21.84	20.97	20.10	19.23
	LCL	13.82	12.90	11.97	11.04	10.12	9.19	8.27	7.34
S7- Model_7:	Forecast	31.13	31.13	31.13	31.13	31.13	31.13	31.13	31.13
	UCL	56.74	56.74	56.74	56.74	56.74	56.74	56.74	56.74
	LCL	5.52	5.52	5.52	5.52	5.52	5.52	5.52	5.52
S8- Model_8:	Forecast	18.65	18.65	18.65	18.65	18.65	18.65	18.65	18.65
	UCL	29.66	29.66	29.66	29.66	29.66	29.66	29.66	29.66
	LCL	7.64	7.64	7.64	7.64	7.64	7.64	7.64	7.64
S9-	Forecast	28.13	28.13	28.13	28.13	28.13	28.13	28.13	28.13

Model_9:	UCL	68.22	68.22	68.22	68.22	68.22	68.22	68.22	68.22
	LCL	-11.96	-11.96	-11.96	-11.96	-11.96	-11.96	-11.96	-11.96
S10-	Forecast	39.23	39.23	39.23	39.23	39.23	39.23	39.23	39.23
Model_10:	UCL	167.13	167.13	167.13	167.13	167.13	167.13	167.13	167.13
	LCL	-88.66	-88.66	-88.66	-88.66	-88.66	-88.66	-88.66	-88.66
S11-	Forecast	26.48	26.48	26.48	26.48	26.48	26.48	26.48	26.48
Model_11:	UCL	46.02	46.02	46.02	46.02	46.02	46.02	46.02	46.02
	LCL	6.94	6.94	6.94	6.94	6.94	6.94	6.94	6.94

Figure 2. Graphical forecasting analysis for I15

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ENTERPRISE DISSOLUTION TRENDS IN A ROMANIAN MOUNTAIN AREA: AN ANALYSIS OF DISSOLUTION RATES DURING THE REFERENCE PERIOD 2008-2018

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Brîndușa Covaci, CBM International University & Centre for Mountain

Economy & Zealandina Agency, USA & UK

Mihai Covaci, CBM International University & Hyperion University &

Zealandina Agency, USA & UK

Abstract:

The economic landscape of any region is subject to constant change, influenced by various factors such as market dynamics, regulatory environments, and local characteristics. In this article, we delve into the intriguing patterns of enterprise dissolution in a specific Romanian mountain area, shedding light on the trends that unfolded during the reference period from 2008 to 2018.

1. Background: Economic Dynamics in Mountainous Regions

Mountain Perspective Journal (1/2023)